

1. Bangladesh Situation Report

According to The Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh (ACT NO. OF 1972), the elections to Parliament shall be based on adult franchise. A person shall be entitled to be enrolled on the electoral roll for a constituency delimited for the purpose of election to the Parliament if he is a citizen of Bangladesh; is not less than eighteen years of age; does not stand declared by a competent court to be of unsound mind; is or is deemed by law to be a resident of that constituency, and has not been convicted of any offence under the Bangladesh Collaborators Special Tribunals Order 1972. ^[1]

When looking at the Voter Registration Process of Bangladesh a continuous register voter data is in use by collected and updated between electoral events. And by using Digital voter registration kits/computers, online connected to a central database that the technology collect voter registration data, both fingerprint scans and photos. ^[2] On the other hand look stage by stage of Bangladesh voter registration process Primary Stage: Preparation of area-based primary estimation of voters on the basis of previous electoral roll. Recruitment of required numbers of assistant registration officers (AROs), one supervisor for every five enumerators and one enumerator for every 300-400 voters on the basis of the estimations. As such recruitments get underway, building awareness among the people about the process by using mass media. Forming various committees comprising local public representatives, and representatives of local administration and civil society to further coordination. Publishing advertisements for the recruitments of area-based data entry operators, team leaders etc., sorting through the received job applications, taking exams and giving appointments. Printing and distribution of Forms for data collection. Preparing registrar books, voter slips and procuring stamp pads for enumerators. Handing the procured goods over to district election officers. Taking steps to enroll voters in jails under special arrangements. Middle Stage: Arranging one-day orientation for assistant registration officers. Imparting three-day training to supervisors and enumerators. Imparting 3-10 days of training to data entry operators and team leaders. Giving the Form and other required items out to enumerators. Collecting of data in Form-2 through door-to-door visits by the enumerators at least 7-10 days ahead of schedules set for photograph-taking. Keeping detailed records of seriously ill and physically or mentally challenged people in registrars. Handing over the collected data to the supervisors and scrutinizing the data received by the supervisors. Handing the scrutinized data by the supervisors to the AROs and upon scrutiny by the AROs. Compiling the data in accordance with areas. Setting up voter registration centers and Upazila/ Thana server stations with assistance from the army. Handing over the registration forms to the registration-center team

leaders by the AROs. Informing AROs about the dates, time and numbers by the team leaders for photograph-taking. Passing the information to enumerators through supervisors by the AROs. By distributing chits/slips, enumerators inform the voters about the time, dates and names of the centers for photographs-taking. Make all arrangements ready at the centers for photograph-taking. Last Stage: Making the registration centers and server stations operational. Procuring and setting up the laptops, webcams, Finger-print scanners, photocopy machines, generators etc. Second Phase: Re-scrutinizing the Forms Obtaining and scrutinizing forms at registration centers. Serializing the forms in laptops. Making entries of the forms in logbooks. Third Phase: Data Collection and Identity Scrutiny at Reg. Centers Voters visiting the centers and handing over the slips to persons on duty. Collecting respective forms and reaching out to the data entry operators. Identifying the voters by scrutinizers present at the centers. Making entries of data in the laptop (unless already entries are made) by the data entry operators. Taking photographs, fingerprints, signatures and handing over the receipts. Completing any incomplete entries by the data entry operators. Daily handover of data in laptops to the team leaders and transfer the same through them to the Upazila-level server stations. Fourth Phase: Registration of Physically Challenged. Jail Inmates, Missed-out Voters and Ailing People Identifying and informing about the voters missed out on the registration. Registering the missed-out voters following the process described in the Third Phase. Completing the registration of the physically challenged and seriously ill people by door-to-door visits (in the last three days). Informing the team leaders about the data of physically challenged and seriously ill people and transferring the data to Upazila servers through them. Collecting data of jail inmates under special arrangements. Completing the registration process by visiting jails and taking the eligible inmates' photographs, fingerprints and signatures. Fifth Phase: Data Processing at Upazila Sewers Sending the data of jail inmates to concerned voter areas and entering those into computers processing all data at Upazila servers. Scrutinizing and improving the standard of data servers. Matching the data preserved at servers. Identifying the duplicate voters. Informing the team leaders. Correcting the errors. Preparing the draft national ID cards and exhibiting the same. Correcting the errors in the draft national ID cards. Preparing the national ID cards and distribution.^[3]

To conclude practical implications on turnout, transparency, sustainability of the actual voter registration system of Bangladesh consider the security of actual votes (both authenticity and secrecy), preventing the loss of valid votes, preventing the addition of fraudulent votes, protecting voter information from damage is transparent and sustainable. Also during the casting vote, the voter cannot cast vote more than once by using the National ID card as a conclusion the practical

implication of the Bangladesh Voter registration system and process leads for better turn out unlike that of the former electoral voter registration system and process.

2. Briefing Note to act to improve the voter registration of Bangladesh

Point One

- **Issue:** Establishment of identity of a citizen in terms of his real name, age, address and occupation
- **Current Status:** It has been the most daunting challenge in preparing an authentic electoral rolls still.
- **Key considerations:** The issue has become all the more crucial due to the fact that entitle him to a number of services provided by the government and other service delivery organizations. The main problem in establishing identity emanates from the prevalence of malpractices in various public sector agencies responsible for issuing certificate on citizenship, residence, birth and death, occupation and other matters. The commission, with the help of the armed forces, has established a checking mechanism for detecting frauds and malpractices and this has worked somehow. But still the system is vulnerable to the activities of miscreants and gangsters.^[4]

Point Two

- **Issue:** Supply chain management & Human Resource issues including Registering some categories of urban voters and capturing fingerprints
- **Current Status:** Large quantity of very valuable inventory is received at the headquarters of the electoral commission that is always from time to time needs to be transferred quickly to the field on the other hand Lack of technical capacity of some data entry operations affect the quality. On the other hand about one fourth areas in Bangladesh are highly inaccessible due to their location in the coastal belt, haor or hilly areas of the country with little or no communication facilities. On the other hand in major metropolitan cities frequent in and out migration lack of residential address and their non-availability during home visits pose serious problems for poor and disadvantaged people to register as voters. Sometimes owners of various industries, shops and establishments do not allow time to their employees to get registered. Even if they are present for registration on the other hand difficulties are experienced in capturing the fingerprints of certain categories of people due to fading of their finger lines while doing arduous manual works.^[5]

- **Key considerations:** Female date entry operators are crucial to the registration process but they are not always found in sufficient numbers and the necessary inventory has to be warehoused, guarded and transported to support the registration schedule, Any Breakdown in the supply chain is a potential risk factor. For the huge number of equipment and other accessories. Considering special transport arrangements are the must to be made with the assistance of the Armed Forces to reach the hard to reach places of Bangladesh. Also The electoral commission had to negotiate with employer's associations and individual owner to grant their employees leave for registration purposes. This will also must be continue to be a major problem and the electoral commission have to take special care to cover these people.

Point Three

- **Issue:** Bangladeshi expatriates' voting rights
- **Current Status:** Bangladesh is one of the few nations which has neither implemented any active steps in ensuring the voting rights of its expatriates, nor is it in the process of doing so in the near future. Yet even a superficial examination of the issue would show that Bangladeshi expatriates probably are more deserving of such rights than many other countries.
- **Key considerations:** A reliable estimate shows that there are approximately nine million Bangladeshis living and working in various parts of the world, representing around 5 percent of the total population of the country. According to the World Bank data, in the last five years, the average yearly remittance sent by expatriates of the country was over USD 14.5 billion, amounting to almost 10 percent of the country's GDP. The Migration and Remittances fact-book 2016, published by the World Bank, shows that in the last few years, Bangladesh has been consistently among the top ten remittance receiving countries in the world. If we disregard smaller countries (countries with population under 10 million), overseas Bangladeshis' contribution to the country's GDP would stand as the highest such contribution by expatriates of any country in the world, except for the Philippines. Thus holding the expatriates interest in the election is must.^[6]

3. Recommendations for reform the voter registration of Bangladesh

From the three Brief notes, we consider and believe Bangladeshi expatriates' voting rights on their voter registration reform policy we think and believe is that may ease the situation in Bangladesh. The following five recommendations address why the change is needed, the process by which the change could be implemented, and what the consequences might be.

1. The estimated nine million Bangladeshi expatriates may be broadly categorized into two groups. The first group consists of those who have migrated to the Middle East and other parts of Asia, generally leaving their families behind, and for work purposes only. This group numbers approximately seven million Bangladeshis and almost all of them are of voting age. Their initial voting registrations can take place while they are in Bangladesh. The second group of two million or so Bangladeshis are those who have settled in the Western countries and their descendants. Thus our first recommendation is that it is necessary to adopt a mechanism for them to be registered for the vote through Bangladeshi Missions abroad. This practice has been successfully adopted by many countries including the Philippines, Poland, Thailand and Ukraine.
2. However, considering the first recommendation there is indeed a provision of voting for the expatriates. Bangladeshi expatriates will be able to exercise their franchises through postal ballots. But the problem is that this is a lengthy process and full of hassles. In this age of technology, this is not a time-effective process. So making the hassle to improve we secondly recommend through Online Electronic Voting System for Abroad Bangladeshi Voter by improving the law.
3. The recommended online electronic voting system is recommended to be with two terminals such as control terminal and registering terminal that the control terminal may be established in the Election Commission of Bangladesh (ECB) and registering terminal may be established in the polling station (in abroad country) which is selected by Election Commission.
4. The Recommended online electronic voting system is recommended to have Voter and Candidate information, their name and photograph will be prepared and loaded into the system through registration management software. District code, seat code, party code, ballot or symbol code and symbol are also prepared and loaded into the system through code management software. After verifying the above content administrator has to print an ID card for each expatriate voter and candidate through registration management software. These ID cards are certified and distributed by the Electoral Commission of Bangladesh through an embassy.
5. The recommended online electronic voting system is recommended to be with block chain technology since the Internet is a public network, all data transfer between voting terminal and control terminal must be performed in encrypted form through Internet using bock chain technology. So unauthorized bodies can't recognize, access and modify these data.

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